

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part V. Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin

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7-Benzoyloxy-6-methoxyisochroman (VII), synthesised by two alternative routes, on CrO₃-oxidation followed by debenylation, furnishes 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin (IX).

It was shown earlier¹ that the preferred route to dihydroisocoumarin synthesis involved the use of appropriate homophthalates as the starting materials; reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, cyclodehydration of the resulting homophthalyl alcohols with fused potassium acid sulphate to isochromans, and subsequent oxidation with chromium trioxide furnished the dihydroisocoumarins. Adopting the same sequence of reactions, the intermediate, 7-benzoyloxy-6-methoxyisochroman (VII), has been synthesised from the homophthalate (V). For this purpose ferulic acid² was reduced to hydroferulic acid³ and cyclised to the known 6-hydroxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one⁴ (I). Cyclisation of hydroferulic acid was effected with sulphuric acid⁵ in about 30% yield and with hydrogen fluoride⁴ in nearly 90% yield, but as hydrogen fluoride was neither available nor possible to be used in our laboratory, we took recourse to cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid which yielded the indan-1-one (I) in 60% yield. It was benzylated to (II) and converted into its isonitroso derivative (III), which on the Beckmann rearrangement with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in alkali, followed by hydrolysis, gave 4-benzoyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetic acid (IV). It was esterified with diazomethane or methanol-sulphuric acid to methyl 4-benzoyloxy-2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate (V); reduction with lithium aluminium hydride and cyclodehydration of the resulting homophthalyl alcohol (VI) with fused potassium acid sulphate furnished 7-benzoyloxy-6-methoxyisochroman (VII).

The isochroman (VII) was also synthesised by an alternative shorter route. Methyl 4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenylacetate (XI), obtained by esterification of 4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenylacetic acid⁶ (X) with diazomethane or methanol-sulphuric acid, was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to 4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (XII). Attempts to prepare the isochroman (VII) from (XII), according to the procedures of Cologne and Boisdé⁷ and of Rieche and Schmitz⁸, gave intractable products.

1. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, Nov. issue.

2. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. I, p. 250.

3. Heilbron, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 1953, 2nd ed., p. 328.

4. Heilmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1386.

5. Konek and Ezamak, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 106.

6. Douglas and Gulland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2896.

7. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 1337.

8. *Chem. Ber.*, 1956, 89, 1254.

Condensation of (XII) with formalin in presence of sulphuric acid at 25-30°, however, introduced the methylol group at the activated 6-position with spontaneous elimination of water *in situ* and yielded the isochroman (VII) in good yield.

3,4-Dihydro-7-benzyloxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII) was next obtained by oxidation of the isochroman (VII) with chromium trioxide; the dihydroisocoumarin (VIII) on debenylation by catalytic hydrogenation over palladised charcoal furnished 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin (IX) in nearly quantitative yield. Methylation of (IX) with diazomethane gave 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin, identical with the authentic specimen prepared earlier⁹ by a different route from 4,5-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (I).—To 4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamic acid⁹ (10 g.) in 5% aqueous $NaOH$ (50 ml) sodium amalgam (350 g., 2.8%) was added in portions with stirring at 55-60° over a period of 6 hrs., the solution being maintained faintly acidic all through by dropwise addition of HCl (dil.). Next day, the filtered solu-

9. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 998.

*All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60-80°.

tion was acidified and extracted repeatedly with a warm mixture of ethyl acetate-chloroform. Removal of the solvent and vacuum distillation of the residue (bath temp. 126.30°/0.5 mm) gave 4-hydroxy-3-methoxydihydrocinnamic acid as plates (9.2 g.), m.p. 89° (lit³. m.p. 89-90°).

The dihydrocinnamic acid (20 g.) was added in one lot to P. P. A. (from P₂O₅ 100 g.+ H₃PO₄ 60 ml, *d* 1.75), maintained at 95-97° and held with stirring for 6 mins. at that temperature. The reaction mixture was poured in excess ice-water and left overnight. The separated solid, on crystallisation from a large volume of boiling water, afforded (I) in golden yellow needles (11 g.), m.p. 194° (lit⁴. m. p. 192.5°). (Found: C, 67.6; H, 5.4. Calc. for C₁₀H₁₀O₃: C, 67.4; H, 5.6%).

6-Benzylloxy-5-methoxyindan-1-one (II).—A thin paste of (I) (17.8 g.), KOH (5.6 g.), benzyl chloride (13 ml), ethanol (125 ml), and water (10 ml) was refluxed for 10 hrs. The excess benzyl chloride was removed by steam distillation, water added to turbidity, and left overnight; the brown solid separating was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from methanol in faintly brown prisms (18 g.). m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 5.6. C₁₇H₁₆O₃ requires C, 76.1; H, 5.97%).

6-Benzylloxy-2-isonitroso-5-methoxyindan-1-one (III).—HCl (conc., 6ml) was added with stirring to the mixture of (II) (9 g.) in methanol (60 ml) and isoamyl nitrite (15 ml), maintained at 50°. The clear solution gradually deposited a crystalline solid, the stirring being continued for 1 hr. at 50°. The reaction mixture was cooled, the precipitate filtered, and washed with cold methanol. Recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished (III) (8.2 g.) as brown needles, m.p. 222° (decomp.). (Found: C, 68.8; H, 5.3; N, 5.0. C₁₇H₁₅O₄N requires C, 68.7; H, 5.1; N, 4.7%).

4-Benzylloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetic Acid (IV).—To a solution of (III) (7 g.) in dioxan (40 ml) and 10% NaOH solution (60 ml) was added portionwise with stirring *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (7.15 g.) at 40-45° and the solution maintained at that temperature with stirring for nearly ½ hour. It was then heated on a water bath for 10 mins., 10% NaOH solution (60 ml) added, the solution refluxed for ½ hrs., and then concentrated by distillation to nearly half its bulk. It was cooled, filtered from a little impurities, and the filtrate acidified with HCl (conc.) when compound (IV) was obtained as a solid (6.3 g.), m.p. 235°. The analytical specimen of (IV) was obtained by crystallisation from a large volume of water in nearly colorless plates, m. p. 238° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.8; H, 5.3. C₁₇H₁₆O₆ requires C, 64.55; H, 5.06%).

Methyl 4-Benzylloxy-2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate (V).—A slurry of (IV) (11 g.) in ether was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane (from 21 g. *N*-nitrosomethylurea). Next day the product (V), which was insoluble in ether, was collected. Further amount of the ester was recovered from the ether solution. Recrystallisation from ethanol yielded the pure ester (V) (10 g.) in white needles, m.p. 123°. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 5.5. C₁₉H₂₀O₆ requires C, 66.3; H, 5.8%).

4-Benzylloxy-2-hydroxymethyl-5-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (VI).—A solution of the ester (6.88 g.) in dry T.H.F. (70 ml) was gradually added with stirring to a slurry of LiAlH₄ (2.4 g.) in dry ether (80 ml) at a rate to maintain a gentle reflux. After the addition, the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs., left overnight, and decomposed by cautious

addition of water until a white granular precipitate was obtained. The filtered ether solution on evaporation left a brown solid which on recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether furnished (VI) in long colorless prisms (4.5 g.), m. p. 101°. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.8. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.80; H, 6.9%).

4-Benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (XII).—A solution of 4-benzoyloxy-3-methoxyphenylacetic acid⁶ (X) (21.6 g.) in methanol (160 ml) was mixed with H_2SO_4 (conc., 4.6 ml) and refluxed for 10 hours; excess methanol was distilled and the reaction solution poured in ice-cold water (250 ml) when the ester (XI) separated as a white solid. It was collected, washed with dilute Na_2CO_3 and water, and dried in an exiccator. The product (20 g.) had m. p. 67°. An analytical sample of (XI) was prepared by recrystallisation from a large volume of petroleum ether in white rhombic needles, m. p. 67°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 71.3; H, 6.3%).

Esterification of the acid (15 g.) in methanol with excess ethereal diazomethane (from 27 g. *N*-nitrosomethylurea) also afforded the methyl ester (15.6 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. 67°.

A solution of the ester (XI) (20 g) in dry ether (150 ml) was reduced with a suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (4.3 g.) in dry ether (150 ml) according to the procedure adopted for the preparation of (VI). The alcohol (XII) (15.2 g.) melted at 71-72°. An analytical specimen was recrystallised from petroleum ether containing a small amount of ethyl acetate in small white plates, m. p. 72°. (Found: C, 74.7; H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 6.9%).

7-Benzoyloxy-6-methoxyisochroman (VII)

Method (a).—An intimate mixture of (VI) (2 g.) and freshly fused potassium acid sulphate (2 g.) was heated for 1 hr. in an oil bath at 140°, the system being connected to an efficient water pump, when most of the water distilled. The reaction mixture was next distilled in *vacuo* and the colorless distillate (b.p. 140-45°/3 mm) soon solidified to a mass of white needles (1.7 g.), m.p. 94-97°. Recrystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether and a few drops of ethyl acetate furnished an analytical specimen of (VII) in white plates, m. p. 100°. (Found: C, 75.7; H, 16.2. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.55; H, 6.6%).

Method (b).—A solution of the alcohol (XII) (1.3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (9 ml) was mixed with formalin (0.6 ml, 40%) and cooled to 25°. H_2SO_4 (conc., 0.6 ml) was next added dropwise with stirring, the temperature of the reaction mixture being maintained at 25° with frequent external cooling. After the addition, the mixture was stirred further for 3½ hrs., the solution was allowed to attain the room temperature (30°), and then poured into crushed ice (25 g.) when a brown solid separated. Next day it was filtered, washed with 2% aq. NaOH and water, and dried in an exiccator. A benzene solution of the product, when chromatographed over Brockmann alumina, afforded the isochroman (VII) as a colorless crystalline solid (1 g.) which was purified as in method (a); m.p. and mixed m.p. 100°.

7-Benzoyloxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (VIII).—To a solution of (VII) (1.05 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) a solution of CrO_3 (1.2 g.) in water (1 ml) and glacial acetic acid (4 ml) was added dropwise with stirring and occasional cooling the

exothermic reaction so as to maintain the temperature at 30°. After the addition, the stirring was continued for 1 hr. more at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then treated with an equal volume of water, extracted with chloroform (20 ml×3), the organic layer washed well with aq. NaHCO₃ and water, dried (Na₂SO₄), and filtered. Evaporation of chloroform left a thick brown oil, a benzene solution of which was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina using the same solvent as eluent. Benzene was distilled and the light yellow oily residue triturated with petroleum ether to afford a crystalline solid. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether furnished pale yellow shining plates (0.7 g.) of (VIII), m. p. 126°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.4. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

3,4-Dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin (IX).—A solution of (VIII) (0.2 g.) in methanol (20 ml) was hydrogenated over 5%Pd-C (0.02 g.) at room temperature until no more hydrogen was absorbed. The filtered solution on evaporation left (IX) as a white solid which crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether in white prismatic needles (0.12 g.), m.p. 167°. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 5.0. C₁₀H₁₀O₄ requires C, 61.85; H, 5.1%).

A sample of compound (IX), on treatment with an excess of ethereal diazomethane, afforded 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin, m. p. 140°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared earlier⁹.

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Received May 28, 1962.